

PRAGMATIC ASPEKTS OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION REFORM

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Annotation: This article presents a scientific analysis of the theory and practice of carrying out significant work on the radical improvement and modernization of the management system at the present stage of the country's development. The activity of the public administration system has contributed to the development of the experience of barchaprogressive speeches that have taken place in recent years.

Key words: Action strategy, concept of administrative reform, modernization, outsourcing, crowdsourcing, paradigm.

1 INTRODUCTION

The current modern stage of the country's development in the process of large-scale reforms in 2017-2021 as a result of the implementation of the Strategy of Actions in the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the introduction of high-quality and effective governance, openness of the economy, the activities of the executive branch, however, its achievements and problems that will be present in any country are determined by how state bodies in this country they carry out their activities.

In addition, the task of increasing the efficiency of the government in the field of public administration is a priority task in the modernization¹ of this system. The indicator is aimed at administrative reforms adopted on September 8, 2017 in the concept, which became a completely new stage in the creation of systemic mechanisms in the reform of public administration in our country. Its main goal is to ensure the full implementation of ongoing reforms, adopted state programs and regulatory documents, to outline in the brochure the activities of public authorities and management capable of timely identification and effective solution of existing problems.

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Historically, both in socio-economic and political terms, it is known that the role of the state in society cannot be denied. Therefore, as in all countries, we have Islamic traditions based on the principles of pragmatism² and economics. At the same time, their

achievement of the Maksud will not be the end of the state, but the application of the experience of all the "progressive changes" that have occurred in recent years to the activities of the public administration system.

All measures within the framework of administrative reforms help to ensure the openness of information about the activities of State bodies under the rule of law. The purpose of this is to make the state more socially cohesive and strong, to bring the state closer to its citizens and to ensure a comprehensive rapprochement of the country.

Also, one of the main lessons of the reforms is administrative management, according to which the nature of the permanent function of the State is being reformed. And for this, as noted above, the successful implementation of administrative reform depends not only on organizational support, but also on the rational organization of executive power and the development of a new order of activity.

Consequently, constitutional - Legalization and administrative-legal activities play a significant role in the implementation of the islohats. The preparation and adoption of regulatory legal documents in this regard is a continuation of the process of reforming the system of behavior of managers, the most necessary "tool" for the implementation of administrative reforms.

In order to ensure the timely and full implementation of the tasks set out in the OECD Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 28, 2018, and in accordance with the concept of administrative reforms, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2019 No. Resolution-5644 "On priority measures to increase the responsibility of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the effectiveness of the implementation of strategic tasks" was signed socio-economic development of the country". adopted. The decree is aimed at radically improving the organization of the government's work, forming a qualitatively new system of executive authorities that meet modern requirements, and ministries based on target indicators,

situations, activities that arise before people. Pragmatism in practice promotes the idea that everything that brings the greatest benefit to a person is necessary to make that person more important.

¹ Modernization (France. moderne - the newest, modern) - update something, give it a modern touch, change it in accordance with modern requirements.

² Pragmatism (Greek: pragmatos - work, action) is a philosophical doctrine. In the 70s of the XIX century, it took shape and developed widely in the United States, which had a great impact on the spiritual life of the country. He regarded the philosophy of the past as having a detached, abstract, observant character from life. Representatives of pragmatism promote the program "Restoration of Philosophy". They believe that philosophy should not consist in the perception of the first foundations of being and cognition, but in solving the problems they face in the process of various life

it is necessary to introduce a system for evaluating the activities of heads of state committees and departments. At the same time, it is necessary to review the current approaches and methods of work of the government, to introduce qualitatively new and innovative methods of organizing its activities, to increase the independence of heads of departments in order to achieve clear results in the implementation of state policy and in the attached areas.

The assumption that the principle of "three definitions", which has been established for centuries in the organization of the executive apparatus, can be implemented: functions, proceed with the implementation of the structure, staff and effective state headquarters. By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2019 "On the introduction of a qualitatively new system for organizing the work of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan", Resolution - 4136 was established as a priority of administrative reforms.

Work is underway to optimize and improve the activities of executive authorities. It is known that at present the law of the Cabinet of Ministers of May 6, 1993 "On the Cabinet of Ministers" does not take into account the powers and issues related to it, the procedure for appointing members, as well as the presentation of the Cabinet of Ministers before the Supreme Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Thus, in the new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Cabinet of Ministers", the Cabinet of Ministers has established measures to assess the activities of ministries, state committees and other public administration bodies and their achievement of targets, taking into account the main criteria for achieving targets.

The implementation of tasks within the framework of events is determined by ensuring a high level of organization, accuracy and efficiency in the implementation of all areas of activity of executive authorities, their competence. To this end, the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 28, 2019 "On additional measures for the phased implementation of the principles of advanced public administration and "smart" management in public administration" dated 959" was adopted. The State Academy of Management under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan". The Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Innovative Development, the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, the Ministry of Information Technology and Communications Development were recommended to study their best practices in the field of public administration of the Republics of Korea, the United Arab Emirates and the Russian Federation. Experience-based learning:

- Gradually introduces the principles of management and "intelligent" management in public administration, which includes distance learning technologies in the system of training, retraining and

professional management for government agencies and organizations;

- Introducing distance education technologies into the system of training, retraining and advanced training of professional managers of state bodies and organizations, it will be necessary to create a "portal of managerial personnel", a similar innovation, which will be implemented. So, in the system of state power and management, the change in the paradigm shows that the new concept of reform should be able to create innovative systems that meet the public demand. In the modern conditions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, tasks are being set to develop administrative procedures aimed at further developing relations between the state and non-governmental organizations, individuals and legal entities, forming a mechanism for entering into interaction between business and authorities, establishing a certain order in the sphere of public administration, helping to achieve a certain result in, The adoption of the law-457 of 08.01.2018 "On Administrative Procedures" has become an important incentive for ministries to analyze their guaranteed mechanisms when considering requests and appeals of citizens.

3 CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In addition, changing the powers and responsibilities of State bodies, optimizing their functions and strengthening their institutional structure, attracting human resources and increasing citizen participation in the process are certainly the main components contributing to the transformation of society. The new stage of the current democratic reforms requires the creation of a system of State power operating on the basis of effective governance. This means that it is not just about the management of the state, but about the open and transparent management of the balkiu, holding a position in accordance with a professional approach without compromising career, openness in management and freedom, a citizen should see how the state is managed, be able to coexist independently as an important arena and subject. It is important that the state power is assumed by those Gifted with the ability to manage time. Only such a mechanism ensures the competitiveness of the state in the political arena. However, in those types of activities where competitiveness is sufficiently formed, bureaucracy is reduced, stability in the development of the country is strengthened.

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